

Tutorial for using hydroPSO to calibrate TUWmodel

Study area: Trancura River Basin, Chile

Mauricio Zambrano-Bigiarini*

Oscar M. Baez-Villanueva†

v1.1 - May 31th, 2026

*Universidad de La Frontera, Temuco, Chile. e-mail:mauricio.zambrano@ufrontera.cl

†Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. e-mail:oscar.baezvillanueva@ugent.be

Contents

1	A bit of history	4
2	Citation	4
3	Required hydroPSO version	4
4	Objective	4
5	hydroPSO	5
6	TUWmodel	5
7	Installation	6
8	Model set up	6
8.1	Loading required packages	6
8.2	General settings	6
8.3	Input data	7
8.4	Model parameters	10
8.5	Wrapper R function implementing TUWmodel for hydroPSO	10
8.5.1	Required variables	10
8.5.2	Minimal hydromodInR function	11
8.6	Running TUWmodel	12
8.6.1	<i>Average</i> parameter set	12
8.6.2	<i>Default</i> parameter set	13
9	Calibrating TUWmodel with hydroPSO	15
9.1	Subsetting for the calibration period	15
9.2	Calibrating only 14 parameters instead of 15	16
9.3	Running the calibration	19
9.4	Basic analysis of calibration results	21
9.5	Plotting calibration results	28
9.5.1	Basic plotting	28
9.5.2	Advanced plotting	29
9.5.3	Plotting only some (more sensitive) parameters	41
9.6	Uncertainty analysis of calibration results	49
9.6.1	Reading all calibration results	49
9.6.2	Weighted quantiles of parameter values	50
9.6.3	Weighted quantiles of model simulations	51
9.6.4	P-factor and R-factor	51
9.6.5	95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)	52
9.6.6	Uncertainty in flow duration curve	53
9.6.7	Some comments about P-factor and R-factor	55
10	Verification analysis	55
10.1	Basic analysis of the verification period	55
10.2	Running behavioural parameter sets	62
10.3	Uncertainty analysis of verification results	63
10.3.1	Reading all verification results	63
10.3.2	Weighted quantiles of model simulations	63
10.3.3	P-factor and R-factor	64
10.3.4	95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)	64
10.3.5	Uncertainty in flow duration curve	65

11 FAQ	67
11.1 How can I parallelise my computations?	67
11.2 Why do I get some warnings after the calibration?	69
11.3 Why the KGE values shown by ggof does not match the one obtained during the optimisation?	70
11.4 Why do I get different results every time that I run hydroPSO with the same input data?	70
11.5 How can I calibrate only a reduced number of model parameters?	70
11.5.1 Model parameters to be calibrated	70
11.5.2 Wrapper R function	70
11.5.3 Running the calibration	71
11.5.4 Plotting results	72
12 Software details	79
13 Version history	79
References	80

1 A bit of history

When development of `hydroPSO` (Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas, 2013) began in 2010, R was not yet a common environment for end-to-end hydrological model calibration. To the best of our knowledge, `topmodel` was then the only hydrological model fully implemented as an R function and available from CRAN. Many operational and research workflows still relied on external model executables, configuration files, and command-line calls. For this reason, the early development of `hydroPSO` focused on providing a flexible optimisation interface for hydrological and environmental models that run as external executables on different operating systems (GNU/Linux, Windows, and macOS), while also allowing the optimisation of native R functions through a global, population-based strategy rather than a local search such as the one usually provided by `optim`.

Since then, R has continued to gain visibility in hydrology because it supports reproducible workflows, transparent data processing, model evaluation, and publication-ready graphics in a single programming environment. Several hydrological models are now available as R packages or R-callable routines, including `TUWmodel`, `airGR`, and `VIC5`. This evolution makes it increasingly useful to have a calibration tool that can interact both with external executable models and with models implemented directly in R.

This tutorial shows how to use `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0` to calibrate the lumped `TUWmodel` hydrological model with hydrometeorological input data included in the `hydroPSO` package. The example is intentionally compact, but it illustrates a workflow that hydrologists can adapt to their own catchments, forcing datasets, objective functions, and model structures. Beyond reproducing the Trancura River Basin application, the tutorial is intended to demonstrate how `hydroPSO` can support transparent, reusable, and extensible calibration experiments within the R ecosystem.

2 Citation

This tutorial is inspired in the original `hydroPSO` vignette (Rojas & Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2012) and several scripts developed by Dr. Zambrano-Bigiarini while he was working at the [Joint Research Center](#) and afterwards. If you find it useful, please cite it as Zambrano-Bigiarini & Baez-Villanueva (2020):

Zambrano-Bigiarini, Mauricio and Baez-Villanueva, Oscar M. (2026). Tutorial for interfacing `hydroPSO` with `TUWmodel`. doi:10.5281/zenodo.20476674. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20476674>.

3 Required `hydroPSO` version

This tutorial was developed for `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0`, released in Github (not in CRAN) in March 2020. Although `hydroPSO` has always been able to optimise generic R functions, earlier versions were primarily designed for models executed through external files and command-line calls. Consequently, versions lower than `0.5-0` keep track of goodness-of-fit values but do not retain model simulations when calibrating an R-based model. Since **v0.5-0**, `hydroPSO` provides full support for R-based hydrological and environmental models, including the storage and post-processing of simulated time series.

4 Objective

The main objective of this tutorial is to show how to use `hydroPSO` to obtain an **acceptable** *best parameter set* for the `TUWmodel` hydrological model. The emphasis is to be practical and reproducible: the document focuses on preparing input data, defining parameter bounds, writing an R wrapper function, running the optimisation, and interpreting the main calibration outputs produced by `hydroPSO`. It is not intended to provide a full theoretical treatment of calibration, verification, sensitivity analysis, or uncertainty analysis¹.

The tutorial deliberately keeps the hydrological interpretation concise. The figures generated throughout the workflow are provided as diagnostic outputs that readers can use to examine model behaviour, parameter

¹Some basic references are provided throughout the text to guide readers who are new to these topics.

sensitivity, residual structure, and predictive uncertainty. This design allows hydrologists to focus on how the software components interact, and then transfer the workflow to their own modelling questions.

5 hydroPSO

`hydroPSO` is a multi-platform and model-independent R package based on Particle Swarm Optimisation [PSO; Kennedy & Eberhart (1995)]. It was designed to support three common tasks in hydrological and environmental modelling: *i*) automatic model calibration; *ii*) sensitivity analysis; and *iii*) assessment and visualisation of calibration results. The package can be coupled with models that use PEST-like template and instruction files, external executables, or native R functions. It also supports parallel execution, which is particularly relevant when the calibrated model is computationally expensive or when large parameter ensembles are required.

PSO is a population-based stochastic optimisation technique that explores a bounded parameter space through a *swarm* of candidate solutions, called particles. Each particle represents a possible parameter set and is evaluated with a user-defined objective function, such as the Kling-Gupta efficiency, Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency, root mean squared error, or any other metric appropriate for the modelling objective. During the search, particles update their position and velocity by combining information from their own best-known location and the best-known location in their neighbourhood. This mechanism allows the algorithm to balance exploration of poorly sampled regions of the parameter space with exploitation of promising parameter combinations.

For hydrological applications, this behaviour is useful because objective-function surfaces are often non-linear, multi-modal, and affected by equifinality. `hydroPSO` does not remove these modelling challenges, but it provides a structured and reproducible way to explore them, document the calibration settings, store model outputs, and analyse behavioural parameter sets. For a detailed description of the package and its hydrological applications, please refer to Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013) and Zambrano-Bigiarini et al. (2013).

6 TUWmodel

`TUWmodel` is a hydrological model developed by the Technical University of Vienna (Viglione & Parajka, 2019) that works at daily or hourly temporal scale and follows the structure of the HBV model (Bergström, 1995). The simulation of the hydrological cycle includes snow accumulation, change of humidity in the soil profile, and surface flow throughout the drainage network. It was validated over 320 basins in Austria (J. Parajka et al., 2007), and it has been used in several other studies Aguayo et al. (2024). In particular, P. Slezniak et al. (2016) evaluated `TUWmodel` in basins with different regimes, and reported that it shows good performance in watersheds with snow cover.

The parameters used by `TUWmodel` to represent the different hydrological processes of a basin are briefly described in Table 1. The range of values used to calibrate each of the parameters was taken from Viglione & Parajka (2019), which slightly modified the ranges proposed by J. Parajka et al. (2007).

ID	Description	Units	Process	Range
SCF	Snow correction factor	-	Snow	0.9 - 1.5
DDF	Degree-day factor	mm/°C/day	Snow	0.0 - 5.0
Tr	Temperature threshold above which precip. is rain	°C	Snow	1.0 - 3.0
Ts	Temperature threshold below which precip. is snow	°C	Snow	-3.0 - 1.0
Tm	Temperature threshold above which melt starts	°C	Snow	-2.0 - 2.0
LPrat	Parameter related to the limit for potential evaporation	-	Evaporation	0.0 - 1.0
FC	Field capacity	mm	Infiltration	0.0 - 600
BETA	Non-linear parameter for runoff production	-	Infiltration	0.0 - 20
cperc	Constant percolation rate	mm/day	Infiltration	0.0 - 8.0
k0	Storage coefficient for very fast response	day	Runoff	0.0 - 2.0
k1	Storage coefficient for fast response	day	Runoff	2.0 - 30
k2	Storage coefficient for slow response	day	Runoff	30 - 250

ID	Description	Units	Process	Range
lsuz	Threshold storage state	mm	Runoff	1.0 - 100
bmax	Maximum base at low flows	day	Runoff	0.0 - 30
croute	Free scaling parameter	day ² /mm	Runoff	0.0 - 50

Table 1: Parameters used by *TUWmodel* to represent the different hydrological processes in a basin.

7 Installation

Install the latest stable version of `hydroPSO` and `TUWmodel`.

```
install.packages("hydroPSO")
install.packages("TUWmodel")
```

Alternatively, you can also try the under-development version of `hydroPSO` (from [Github](#)):

```
if (!require(devtools)) install.packages("devtools")
library(devtools)
install_github("hzambran/hydroPSO")
```

Install the latest stable version of `hydroTSM` and `hydroGOF`. These packages will be used to evaluate the performance of the simulated streamflow.

```
install.packages("hydroTSM")
install.packages("hydroGOF")
```

8 Model set up

8.1 Loading required packages

The `hydroPSO` and `TUWmodel` packages include all the data and functions used in this analysis. The `hydroTSM` (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026b) and `hydroGOF` (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026a) packages are used here to manipulate the hydrological time series and to compute the modified Kling-Gupta efficiency [KGE³; Kling et al. (2012), Gupta et al. (2009)], respectively.

```
library(zoo)
library(TUWmodel)
library(hydroPSO)
library(hydroTSM)
library(hydroGOF)
```

8.2 General settings

The variable `model.drty` will be used as the parent directory where all the output files generated during the calibration of the hydrological model will be stored.

```
# modify it according to your specific paths
#model.drty <-"/home/hzambran/GIT/vignettes/vignette_output/vignette_output"
model.drty <-"/Users/hzambran/GIT/vignettes/hydroPSO_vignettes/vignette_output"
```

The variable `PSO.drty.out` represents the output directory that will store all the files generated by the `hydroPSO` function during the calibration of the `TUWmodel` hydrological model. It is not necessary to create this directory before running the calibration, because if this directory does not exist, it is automatically created by the `hydroPSO` function.

```
PSO.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "PSO.out")
```

The variable `Figures.drty.out` represents the output directory that will store all the figures generated during the analysis of the calibration and verification results.

```
Figures.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "Figures")
```

```
# If the output directory selected to store the figures does not exist, it is created:  
if (!file.exists(Figures.drty.out)) dir.create(Figures.drty.out, recursive=TRUE)
```

Setting up the calibration (1979-1997) and verification (1998-2016) periods, each one of them include 1 year of warming up (see Section 9.2):

```
### Calibration period  
Cal.Ini <- "1980-01-01"  
Cal.Fin <- "1997-12-31"  
  
### Verification period  
Ver.Ini <- "1999-01-01"  
Ver.Fin <- "2016-12-31"  
  
### Starting date of the warm-up period, one for calibration and other for verification  
Warmup.Ini.Cal <- "1979-01-01"  
Warmup.Ini.Ver <- "1998-01-01"
```

8.3 Input data

The study area for this tutorial is a subcatchment of the Trancura River Basin, which is located in the Araucania Region in Southern Chile. In particular, our study area drains into the “Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco” streamflow station (COD.BNA:9414001).

In order to run `TUWmodel` you only need daily time series of precipitation, mean air temperature and potential evapotranspiration. Daily time series of precipitation (P [mm/day]), mean air temperature ($Temp$ [°C]), potential evaporation (PET [mm/day]), and streamflow (Q [m³/s]) from 1979-2016 were downloaded from the CAMELS-CL dataset (Alvarez-Garreton et al., 2018). In particular, precipitation and mean air temperature data correspond to spatially-averaged mean daily values (CR2met), while potential evapotranspiration values were computed using the Hargreaves-Samani equation based on the maximum and minimum air temperature data.

All the time series are provided since the 0.5-0 version of the `hydroPSO` package, but of course you can use your own local data files and read them into R.

Specifying the catchment area, [m²):

```
Area.m2 <- 1415025887
```

Specifying the name and ID of the discharge station used as outlet of the study area (they will be used afterwards, in the title of some figures during the analysis of the calibration results):

```
Qobs.stationname <- "Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco"  
Qobs.ID <- "9414001"
```

Loading the daily meteorological input data (P, Temp, and PET) and the observed discharges at the outlet of the catchment as a single data.frame object, with values from 01-Jan-1979 to 31-Dec-2016:

```
data(Trancura9414001)
```

Creating individual time series of P, Temp, PET and Qobs:

```
dates <- Trancura9414001[, 1]
P      <- Trancura9414001[, 2]
Temp   <- Trancura9414001[, 3]
PET    <- Trancura9414001[, 4]
Qobs   <- Trancura9414001[, 5]
```

It is worth mentioning that to **run** TUWmodel you do not need values of observed discharges at the outlet of your catchment. However, to **calibrate** your model you must provide observed discharge values (with the same temporal frequency of the model simulations), in order to be able to compute the user-defined goodness-of-fit measure between your model simulations and their corresponding observed values.

Transforming the previously created numeric values and their corresponding dates into zoo objects:

```
dates    <- as.Date(dates)
P.zoo    <- zoo::zoo(P, dates)
Temp.zoo <- zoo::zoo(Temp, dates)
PET.zoo  <- zoo::zoo(PET, dates)
Qobs.zoo <- zoo::zoo(Qobs, dates)
```

Daily discharges simulated by TUWmodel are expressed in mm/day, but the previously loaded observed discharges are in m³/s. Therefore, in order to correctly compare the observations (m³/s) with the simulated values obtained from TUWmodel (in mm/day) it is necessary to convert the observed discharges from m³/s to mm/day:

```
# 1 day = 86400 s
Qobs.zoo <- (Qobs.zoo * 1000 * 86400) / Area.m2
```

Plotting the full time series of meteorological input data (P, Temp, PET) and the observed discharges (Qobs):

```
par(mfrow=c(4,1), mar = c(2, 3.5, 1, 1), oma=c(0, 0, 0, 0), mgp=c(2, 0.75, 0) )
plot(P.zoo    , xlab="Time", col="lightblue", main="Precipitation"      , ylab="P [mm/day]")
grid()
plot(Temp.zoo, xlab="Time", col="red"       , main="Air temperature"      , ylab="Temp [degC]" )
grid()
plot(PET.zoo , xlab="Time", col="darkgreen", main="Potential evaporation", ylab="PET [mm/day]")
grid()
plot(Qobs.zoo, xlab="Time" , col="blue"    , main="Observed streamflows" , ylab="Q, [mm]" )
grid()
```


Figure 1: Daily values of precipitation, air temperature, potential evapotranspiration and streamflows for the Trancura River Basin during the 1970-2016 time period.

8.4 Model parameters

It is not a requirement for `hydroPSO`, but setting the names of the `TUWmodel` model parameters will make easier the interpretation of the calibration results. In addition, the lower and upper boundaries for each one of the parameters of the `TUWmodel` are defined following Viglione & Parajka (2019):

```
names <- c("SCF", "DDF", "Tr", "Ts", "Tm", "LPrat", "FC", "Beta",
           "k0", "k1", "k2", "lsuz", "cperc", "bmax", "croute")
lower <- c( 0.9, 0.0, 1.0, -3.0, -2.0, 0.0, 0, 0,
           0, 2, 30, 1, 0, 0, 0)
upper <- c( 1.5, 5.0, 3.0, 1.0, 2.0, 1.0, 600, 20,
           2, 30, 250, 100, 8, 30, 50)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

8.5 Wrapper R function implementing TUWmodel for hydroPSO

For the calibration of `TUWmodel` (or any other hydrological model implemented as an R function), you must build an R function that provides the outputs used by `hydroPSO` to move forward in the parameter space throughout the iterations. **This function MUST fulfil the following requirements:**

- 1) Its first argument must be named `param.values`, which represents the numeric values of the parameters to be optimised. The values for the `param.values` argument are created internally by `hydroPSO` during the optimisation.
- 2) One of its arguments must be named `obs`, which represents the observed values. `obs` are used to be compared against the simulated values delivered by the hydrological model (`sim`)
- 3) It must return a list object with -at least- the following elements:
 - 3.1) **GoF**: the goodness-of-fit obtained when the hydrological model is run with `param.values` as parameter set.
 - 3.2) **sim**: model output obtained when the hydrological model is run with `param.values` as parameter set. It MUST have the same object class and dimensions as the observed values provided by the user in `obs`.

8.5.1 Required variables

`TUWmodel` does not support `zoo` objects as input data, and works with plain numeric values. Therefore, we need to transform the input time series into numeric objects:

```
P <- as.numeric(P.zoo)
Temp <- as.numeric(Temp.zoo)
PET <- as.numeric(PET.zoo)
Qobs <- as.numeric(Qobs.zoo)
```

The input data used for the calibration-period diagnostic runs include one year of warm-up before the period used to compute the goodness-of-fit:

```
P.zoo.cal <- window(P.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
Temp.zoo.cal <- window(Temp.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
PET.zoo.cal <- window(PET.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)

P.cal <- as.numeric(P.zoo.cal)
Temp.cal <- as.numeric(Temp.zoo.cal)
PET.cal <- as.numeric(PET.zoo.cal)
```

```

Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
dates.cal    <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)
warmup.days  <- hydroTSM::dip(from=Warmup.Ini.Cal,
                             to=(as.Date(Cal.Ini)-1),
                             out.type="nbr"
                             )

```

8.5.2 Minimal hydromodInR function

The package-level `hydromodInR()` function is used below for direct diagnostic runs. With the current interface, a single named numeric vector can be passed directly through `Particles`; `hydromodInR()` converts it internally to a one-row parameter set, injects it into `model.FUN.args` as `param.values`, and then calls the user-defined `TUWmodel_hydromodInR()` model function.

```

TUWmodel_hydromodInR <- function(param.values,
                                obs,
                                dates,
                                warmup.days = 365,
                                P,
                                Temp,
                                PET,
                                Area = Area.m2,
                                gof.FUN = "KGE",
                                gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")) {

  # Running the TUWmodel model
  simLump <- TUWmodel(param = param.values, prec = P, airt = Temp,
                     ep = PET, area = Area)

  # Getting the outputs simulated by the CemaNeige-GR6J model
  qsim <- as.numeric(simLump$q)
  qsim <- qsim[(warmup.days + 1):length(qsim)]
  sim  <- zoo::zoo(qsim, dates)

  # Computing model's performance
  gof.args <- modifyList(gof.FUN.args, list(sim = sim, obs = obs))
  gof      <- do.call(gof.FUN, gof.args)

  # Creating the output of the R function
  out <- list(GoF = gof, sim = sim)

  return(out)
} # 'TUWmodel_hydromodInR' END

```

The arguments that remain fixed across all calibration-period model runs are stored in `model.FUN.args`. In direct diagnostic calls, the candidate parameter vector is passed directly to `hydromodInR()` through `Particles`:

```
model.FUN.args <- list(obs = Qobs.zoo.cal,
                      dates = dates.cal,
                      warmup.days = warmup.days,
                      P = P.cal,
                      Temp = Temp.cal,
                      PET = PET.cal,
                      Area = Area.m2,
                      gof.FUN = "KGE",
                      gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")
                    )
```

8.6 Running TUWmodel

The `hydromodInR()` function can now be called directly for simple diagnostic runs before calibration.

8.6.1 Average parameter set

Before any calibration of `TUWmodel` we must be sure that the model is able to run correctly with the previously prepared input data. As first guess, we will use as parameter set the *average* between the lower and upper boundary of each model parameter:

```
params <- lower + (upper - lower) / 2
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = params,
                           model.FUN = TUWmodel_hydromodInR,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

The output returned by `hydromodInR()` includes the simulated streamflow and the goodness-of-fit value required by `hydroPSO`:

```
str(modeloutput)
```

```
## List of 2
## $ GoF: num 0.278
## $ sim:'zoo' series from 1980-01-01 to 1997-12-31
## Data: num [1:6575] 2.73 2.71 2.69 2.67 2.66 ...
## Index: Date[1:6575], format: "1980-01-01" "1980-01-02" ...
```

Extract only the simulated streamflows from the full model output:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
Qsim <- as.numeric(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

The direct `hydromodInR()` call returns the simulated streamflow as a `zoo` object. The following object stores the associated dates for consistency with the rest of the vignette:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphical comparison of **daily observed and simulated time series** obtained with the *average* parameter set:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [mm]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 2: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Not too bad (except for low flows), but let's try the default parameter values suggested by Viglione & Parajka (2019) ...

8.6.2 Default parameter set

As second guess, we will use as parameter set the *default* values for each model parameter, as defined in the manual of the TUWmodel R package (Viglione & Parajka, 2019):

```
params      <- c(1.2, 1.2, 2, -2, 0, 0.9, 100, 3.3,
                0.5, 9, 105, 50, 2, 10, 26.5)
names(params) <- names

modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = params,
                           model.FUN = TUWmodel_hydromodInR,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

Extracting only simulated streamflows from the full model output:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
Qsim <- as.numeric(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

The direct `hydromodInR()` call returns the simulated streamflow as a `zoo` object. The following object stores the associated dates for consistency with the rest of the vignette:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphical comparison of **daily observed and simulated time series** obtained with the *default* parameter set:

```
ggof( sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [mm]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 3: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Better than the previous parameter set, but here is still plenty of space for improving these simulated values. . .

9 Calibrating TUWmodel with hydroPSO

9.1 Subsetting for the calibration period

For the calibration of TUWmodel with hydroPSO we are going to use only a portion of the available input time series, leaving the rest for an independent verification period:

```
P.zoo.cal    <- window(P.zoo    , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
Temp.zoo.cal <- window(Temp.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
PET.zoo.cal  <- window(PET.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Because the model outputs returned by TUWmodel are evaluated after the warm-up period, the observations (Qobs) must be subset to the same simulation period before they are compared with the simulated streamflows:

```
Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Store the dates associated with the period used to evaluate the calibration outputs:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)
```

As mentioned before, TUWmodel does not support zoo objects as input data, and works with plain numeric values. Therefore, we need to transform the input time series into numeric objects:

```
P.cal      <- as.numeric(P.zoo.cal)
Temp.cal   <- as.numeric(Temp.zoo.cal)
PET.cal    <- as.numeric(PET.zoo.cal)
warmup.days <- length(window(P.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Cal,
                             end=as.Date(Cal.Ini) - 1))
```

```
model.FUN.args <- modifyList(model.FUN.args,
                             list(obs = Qobs.zoo.cal,
                                   dates = dates.cal,
                                   warmup.days = warmup.days,
                                   P = P.cal,
                                   Temp = Temp.cal,
                                   PET = PET.cal,
                                   Area = Area.m2
                             )
)
```

9.2 Calibrating only 14 parameters instead of 15

To reduce over-parameterisation and structural equifinality in the calibration of `TUWmodel`, we follow Széles et al. (2020) and Baez-Villanueva et al. (2021) by reducing the number of free parameters from 15 to 14 through a deterministic constraint on precipitation-phase partitioning.

`TUWmodel` includes 15 core parameters distributed across its snow, soil-moisture, and runoff-routing routines (see Section 6). In the snow routine, the critical temperature thresholds `T_r` and `T_s` define the transition interval for mixed precipitation: precipitation is classified entirely as rain above `T_r` and entirely as snow below `T_s`. Rather than calibrating `T_r` and `T_s` as independent unconstrained parameters, we tie both thresholds to a single **wet-bulb temperature threshold**, `T_wb`, such that $T_r = T_s = T_{wb}$. This identity constraint removes one degree of freedom, collapses the two precipitation-phase thresholds into a single calibrated parameter, and reduces the calibration space to 14 active parameters while preserving the mass-balance structure governing snow accumulation and melt.

The implementation of this identity constraint leads to the following updated definition of the 14 calibrated parameters:

```
names <- c("SCF", "DDF", "Twb", "Tm", "LPrat", "FC", "Beta",
          "k0", "k1", "k2", "lsuz", "cperc", "bmax", "croute")
lower <- c( 0.9, 0.0, -3.0, -2.0, 0.0, 0, 0,
           0, 2, 30, 1, 0, 0, 0)
upper <- c( 1.5, 5.0, 3.0, 2.0, 1.0, 600, 20,
           2, 30, 250, 100, 8, 30, 50)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

To transform the 14 calibrated parameters into the 15 model parameters required by `TUWmodel`, we define the helper function `to_TUWmodel_param`, as follows:

```
to_TUWmodel_param <- function(param.values) {

  if (length(param.values) == 14) {
    param.values <- c(param.values[1:2], param.values[3], param.values[3], param.values[4:14])
  } # IF end

  if (length(param.values) != 15) {
    stop("TUWmodel requires 15 parameters; got ", length(param.values), ".")
  } else
    names(param.values) <- c("SCF", "DDF", "Tr", "Ts", "Tm", "LPrat", "FC", "BETA",
                           "k0", "k1", "k2", "lsuz", "cperc", "bmax", "croute")

  return( param.values )
} # 'to_TUWmodel_param' END
```

Accordingly, the previously defined TUWhydromod.basic function is updated as follows:

```
TUWhydromod.basic <- function(param.values,      # it MUST be present
                              obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, # it MUST be present
                              dates=dates.cal,  # Optional
                              warmup.days=warmup.days, # Optional
                              P=P.cal,          # Optional
                              Temp=Temp.cal,    # Optional
                              PET=PET.cal,      # Optional
                              Area=Area.m2,     # Optional
                              gof.FUN="KGE",    # Optional
                              gof.FUN.args=list(method="2012") # Optional
                              ) {

  # "SCF" "DDF" "Twb" "Tm" "LPrat" "FC" "Beta" "k0" "k1" "k2" "lsuz" "cperc" "bmax" "croute"
  #param.values2 <- c(param.values[1:2], param.values[2:14])
  param.values2 <- to_TUWmodel_param(param.values)

  # Evaluating the hydrological model at the 'param.values' parameter set
  simLump <- TUWmodel(param=param.values2, prec=P, airt=Temp, ep=PET, area=Area)

  # Extracting only the evaluated-period streamflows
  qsim <- as.numeric(simLump$q)
  qsim <- qsim[(warmup.days+1):length(qsim)]
  sim <- zoo::zoo(qsim, dates)

  # Computing the goodness-of-fit value (i.e, model performance)
  gof.args <- modifyList(gof.FUN.args, list(sim=sim, obs=obs))
  gof      <- do.call(gof.FUN, gof.args)

  # Creating the output of the R function
  out <- list(GoF=gof, sim=sim)

  return(out)
} # 'TUWhydromod.basic' end
```

Similarly, the previously defined TUWhydromod function is updated as follows:

```
TUWhydromod <- function(param.values,      # it MUST be present
                        obs=Qobs.zoo.cal,  # it MUST be present
                        dates=dates.cal,   # Optional
                        warmup.days=365,   # Optional, 1 year of warming up
                        P=P.cal,           # Optional
                        Temp=Temp.cal,     # Optional
                        PET=PET.cal,       # Optional
                        Area=Area.m2       # Optional
                        ) {

  # "SCF" "DDF" "Twb" "Tm" "LPrat" "FC" "Beta" "k0" "k1" "k2" "lsuz" "cperc" "bmaæ" "croute"
  #param.values2 <- c(param.values[1:2], param.values[2:14])
  param.values2 <- to_TUWmodel_param(param.values)

  # Evaluating the hydrological model at the 'param.values' parameter set
  simLump <- TUWmodel(param=param.values2, prec=P, airt=Temp, ep=PET, area=Area)

  # Extracting only the numeric vector with simulations and observations
  qsim <- as.numeric(simLump$q)

  # Converting model simulations into zoo objects
  qsim.zoo.full <- zoo::zoo(qsim, dates)

  # Removing the warm-up period (one year, i.e., 365 days)
  n      <- length(qsim.zoo.full)
  qsim.zoo <- qsim.zoo.full[(warmup.days+1):n]
  obs     <- obs[(warmup.days+1):n]

  # Computing the goodness-of-fit value (i.e, model performance)
  gof     <- KGE(sim=qsim.zoo, obs=obs, method="2012")

  # Creating the output of the R function
  out <- list(GoF=gof, sim=qsim.zoo.full)

  return(out)
} # 'TUWhydromod' end
```

9.3 Running the calibration

The TUWmodel model can now be calibrated with `hydroPSO` using `fn = "hydromodInR"` and the `model.FUN.args` list defined above:

```
set.seed(1000)
out <- hydroPSO(fn = "hydromodInR",
               lower = lower, upper = upper, method = "spsso2011",
               control = list(write2disk = TRUE, drty.out = PSO.drty.out,
                              MinMax = "max", npart = 80, maxit = 50,
                              normalise = TRUE, REPORT = 10,
                              parallel = "none", reltol = 1E-10),
               model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
               model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
               )
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `hydroPSO` are briefly explained below (more information can be found with `?hydroPSO`):

- a) **fn**: character, used to tell `hydroPSO` that it will have to optimise an R-based hydrological model.
- b) **lower**: numeric, representing the lower boundaries of each one of the model parameters.
- c) **upper**: numeric, representing the upper boundaries of each one of the model parameters.
- d) **method**: character, used to define the PSO algorithm used to calibrate the hydrological model.
- e) **model.FUN**: R function, used to run the hydrological model (delivering model simulations and their corresponding goodness-of-fit value), fulfilling the three (3) requirements mentioned in Section 9.2.
- f) **model.FUN.args**: list object, contains all the arguments used to run the hydrological model (in addition to `param.values`).
- g) **control**: list object containing the arguments used to fine-tune the calibration with `hydroPSO`. The arguments passed to `control` affect how `hydroPSO` explores the parameter space and how optimisation outputs are written. Particular attention should be given to the following:
 - *drty.out*: character, with the full path to directory that will store the output files of `hydroPSO`, only used when `write2disk=FALSE`. By default `drty.out="PSO.out"` which is looked for within the current working directory. If `drty.out` does not exist, it is automatically created by `hydroPSO` with an informative warning message.
 - *write2disk*: logical, indicates whether the output files will be written to the disk or not. By default `write2disk=TRUE`. If you are only interested in the *optimum* parameter set found by `hydroPSO` and the corresponding simulated values obtained when running SWAT+ with that parameter set, you should set `write2disk=FALSE`, to reduce the storage used in your computer and to reduce the total computation time (because internal files are not written to disk). However, if you set `write2disk=FALSE` you will not be able to use the `plot_results` function, because it requires the internal files created by `hydroPSO` when `write2disk=TRUE`.
 - *MinMax*: character string indicating whether the calibration solves a maximisation or minimisation problem. Valid values are `c('min', 'max')`. The default value is `"min"`.
 - *npart*: numeric value defining the number of particles in the swarm. By default, `npart=NA`, which means that the swarm size depends on the selected method: `npart=ceiling(10+2*sqrt(n))2` when `method='spsso2007'`, or `npart=40` otherwise.
 - *maxit*: numeric, maximum number of iterations. By default `maxit=1000`.

²*n* is the number of model parameters being calibrated.

- *Xini.type*: character, indicates how to initialise the particles' positions in the swarm within the ranges defined by `lower` and `upper`. By default `Xini.type='random'` (random initialisation of positions). However, you might want to try `Xini.type='lhs'` (Latin Hypercube initialisation), or `Xini.type='sobol'` (since `hydroPSO>=0.6`, for quasi-random initialisation of particle's positions using uniform Sobol low discrepancy numbers).
- *boundary.wall*: sometimes PSO fails to keep particles within the valid search space. This argument addresses this by defining exactly how out-of-bounds particles are managed. The specific values it can take are:
 - `NA`: The default setting. It automatically applies either `absorbing2007` or `absorbing2011` depending on the chosen optimisation method.
 - `absorbing2011`: Clamps the particle's position to the boundary edge but flexibly modifies its velocity, allowing it to smoothly 'slide' along the wall rather than stopping completely.
 - `absorbing2007`: A strict clamp that locks the particle to the edge and zeroes its velocity. The particle remains stuck without momentum until algorithmic forces pull it back inside.
 - `reflecting`: Acts as a perfectly elastic surface. It mirrors the particle back inside and exactly reverses its velocity, preserving kinetic energy for continuous, aggressive exploration.
 - `damping`: Functions as an inelastic collision. It reflects the particle back into the space but applies a random reduction to its reversed velocity to bleed off kinetic energy and prevent endless oscillation.
 - `invisible`: Mathematically ignores the boundaries, allowing particles to fly freely outside without altering position or velocity. Out-of-bounds fitness is not evaluated; the particle relies on the attraction of its historical bests to eventually return.
- *normalise*: logical, indicates whether the parameter values have to be normalised to the [0,1] interval during the optimisation or not. It is recommended to use this option when the search space is not an hypercube. By default `normalise=FALSE`.
- *reltol*: numeric, relative convergence tolerance. By default to `reltol=sqrt(.Machine$double.eps)`, typically, about 1e-8.
- *REPORT*: numeric, indicates the frequency of report messages printed to the screen. Default to every 100 iterations. Only used when `verbose=TRUE`.
- *parallel*: character, indicates how to parallelise `hydroPSO`. By default `parallel="none"`. Other possible values are: `parallel="parallel"` (for unix-alike machines) and `parallel="parallelWin"` (for MS Windows machines).
- *par.nnodes*: numeric, indicates the number of cores/CPU's to be used in the local multi-core machine, or the number of nodes to be used in the network cluster. By default `par.nnodes=NA`, which assigns `par.nnodes=parallel::detectCores()` only when `parallel!="none"`.
- *par.pkgs*: list of package names (as characters) that need to be loaded on each node for allowing the objective function `fn` to be evaluated. By default `par.pkgs=list()`. Used only when `parallel="parallelWin"`.

The maximum number of model evaluations during calibration is approximately `npart * maxit`, and the **total execution time** depends on both the cost of one model run and the number of evaluations required by the optimisation. This makes the choice of swarm size (`npart`) and the maximum number of iterations (`maxit`) a practical compromise between search robustness and computational cost.

Using `npart=40` should be good enough for most model applications. However, if the number of parameters of your model is ~10 or more, I suggest to **explore the use of a larger number of particles in combination with a lower number of model runs** (e.g., `npart=80` and `maxit=50`). The later ensures that `hydroPSO` will have enough number of particles to effectively tackle the *curse of dimensionality*, and help to reduce premature convergence, which is particularly relevant for hydrological models affected by parameter interactions, threshold behaviour, and equifinality.

9.4 Basic analysis of calibration results

Looking at the *best* parameter set obtained during the calibration and its corresponding goodness-of-fit value:

```
# 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration
out$par

##          SCF          DDF          Twb          Tm          LPrat          FC
## 0.9479934 2.7817420 2.3314931 -1.7538722 0.9018634 142.3232679
##      Beta          k0          k1          k2          lsuz          cperc
## 0.1088992 0.4018424 13.5379904 34.1717400 74.7525659 6.9515340
##      bmax      croute
## 0.9756327 24.8846980

# goodness-of-fit obtained for the 'best' parameter set
out$value

## [1] 0.8515034
```

Saving the *best* parameter set obtained during the calibration:

```
best.param.cal <- out$par
```

Running TUWmodel with the *best* parameter set obtained during the calibration:

```
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = best.param.cal,
                           model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

Extracting the simulated streamflow returned by hydromodInR():

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
```

Defining a customised title for all the following figures:

```
main <- paste0("TUWmodel: ", Qobs.stationname, "(", Qobs.ID, ")")
```

Graphical comparison of the original daily observed and simulated time series obtained with the *best* parameter set for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, main=main,
     ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 4: Graphical comparison of streamflows simulated by ‘TUWmodel‘ during the calibration period using several performance indices.

Much better than the results obtained with the average default parameter sets, right?

Graphical comparison of **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.cal}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.cal}$) values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 5: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="ma",
     pt.style="bar", FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 6: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **seasonal** simulated and observed values (one plot for each weather season) for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [mm]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 7: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Computing the **daily residuals** for the calibration period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.cal - Qobs.zoo.cal
```

Plotting **daily, monthly and annual** time series, boxplots and histograms of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 8: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Seasonal time series and boxplots of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",  
          season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),  
          h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 9: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the seasonal scale.

9.5 Plotting calibration results

Customised title for all the figures in this section:

```
main <- paste0("TUWmodel: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
```

9.5.1 Basic plotting

The function `plot_results` included in `hydroPSO` can automatically plot several figures that will help you to evaluate how good are the results of the calibration procedure. This function, internally calls the `read_results` function and then produces the following eleven (11) figures:

- 1) Dotty plots of parameter values.
- 2) Histograms of parameter values.
- 3) Boxplots of parameter values.
- 4) Correlation matrix among parameter values (optional).
- 5) Empirical CDFs of parameter values.
- 6) Parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 7) (pseudo) 3D dotty plots of (selected) parameter values.
- 8) GoF for each particle against Number of Model Evaluations.
- 9) Velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 10a) Scatterplot between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `MinMax` is provided).
- 10b) Empirical CDFs for model's output (only produced if `obs` is NOT a zoo object).
- 10b) ggof (See `?ggof`) between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 10d) Empirical CDFs for selected quantiles of model's output (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 11) Convergence Measures (`Gbest` and `normSwarmRadius`) vs Iteration Number.

You can try the basic automatic plotting of the calibration results into the current graphic device (usually, your screen) with:

```
plot_results()
```

9.5.2 Advanced plotting

Notwithstanding the automatic plotting of the calibration results might be good enough for most purposes, you should read `?plot_results` and customise some of its arguments for getting figures that fulfil your case-specific needs:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
            do.png=TRUE,           # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
            params.png.width=630,  # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
            params.png.height=855, # 9.5 inches equals 855 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
            MinMax="max",          # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
            beh.thr=0.3,           # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
            ftype="dm",            # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
            nrows=5,               # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
            FUN=mean,              # function used to compute monthly values
            do.pairs=TRUE,         # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
            gof.name="KGE2012",    # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
            legend.pos="right",    # position of the legend in the convergence plot
            main=main              # user-defined title for most of the output figures
        )
```

```
## [                               ]
## [      Reading output files ... ]
## [                               ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs           : 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 50 ]
##
```

```

## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 80 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
## [
                                ]
## [           Plotting ...     ]
## [
                                ]
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotted plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottedPlots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting 3D dotted plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]
## |
                                |

```

All the figures generated by the previous call to `plot_results` are **not discussed in detail in this tutorial**, but you can read some descriptions about them on Rojas & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2012), Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013), Abdelaziz & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2014) and Abdelaziz et al. (2019).

9.5.2.1 Convergence along iterations

This figure shows the change in the **objective function** (black line) and the change in the **normalised swarm radius** (a measure of swarm spread on the search space) along with the number of iterations used in the optimisation. This figure can be used to obtain a founded guess about the minimum number of iterations required to obtain a satisfactory value of the objective function.

Figure 10: Evolution of global optimum (i.e., KGE2012) and the normalized swarm radius against the number of iterations.

9.5.2.2 Histograms

This figure shows **histograms** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (KGE2012 \geq beh.thr). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)

Figure 11: Histograms of parameter values for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ('KGE2012 \geq beh.thr'). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.5.2.3 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)

Figure 12: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of parameter values for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.5.2.4 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of parameter values versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)

Figure 13: Dotty plots showing the model performance of behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.5.2.5 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of parameter values, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (KGE2012 \geq beh.thr). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)

Figure 14: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of parameter values. Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5, and vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5.

9.5.2.6 3D dotted plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo three-dimensional dotted plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 15: Three-dimensional dotted plots to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

9.5.2.7 Correlation matrix

This figure shows **correlation matrix** between parameters and model performance (KGE2012), considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE2012 \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines represents are fitted to all the pair of points using a lowess smoother, i.e., a locally-weighted polynomial regression.

Figure 16: Correlation matrix between parameters and model performance (KGE2012). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines represents are fitted to all the pair of points using a lowess smoother.

9.5.2.8 Daily and monthly evaluation

This figure shows a **comparison of daily** (upper panel) and **monthly** (lower panel) **streamflows**, obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation, against their corresponding observed counterparts.

Figure 17: Comparison of daily (upper panel) and monthly (lower panel) streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set against their corresponding observed counterparts.

9.5.2.9 Scatterplot of daily values

This figure shows a **Scatterplot** comparing observed streamflows against the simulated values obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation.

Figure 18: Scatterplot of daily streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration and their corresponding observed counterparts.

9.5.2.10 Evaluation of low, medium and high streamflows

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by **TUWmodel** during the calibration period. The previous quantiles were selected as representative of low, medium and high streamflows, respectively. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed 5, 50 and 95 quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles. Therefore, this figure is useful to assess the bias of model results in the low, medium and high part of the simulates time series.

Figure 19: Empirical CDFs (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by **extttTUWmodel** during the calibration period. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed 5, 50 and 95 quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles.

9.5.3 Plotting only some (more sensitive) parameters

In addition to what was mentioned in the previous (Section 9.5.2), you can customise the `plot_results` function a bit further by plotting only **the most sensitive model parameters** obtained during the calibration, in order to analyse their interactions and explore whether it would be a good idea to reduce some parameters in a subsequent calibration round.

You can utilize the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs) of model parameters extracted from `hydroPSO` calibration archives to identify the most sensitive and identifiable parameters. For each parameter, plot and compare the ECDF of the behavioural (acceptable) parameter sets against the ECDF of the initial prior distribution—which appears as a 1:1 diagonal line if a uniform distribution was used for sampling. Parameters showing a strong deviation from this prior line have been heavily conditioned by the calibration process, indicating high identifiability Hornberger & Spear (1981). To formally evaluate sensitivity, you should compare the separation between the behavioural and non-behavioural ECDFs. A pronounced separation or narrowing of these curves indicates that the parameter heavily influences model performance, rendering it sensitive and well-constrained. Conversely, if the curves nearly overlap, the parameter is insensitive to the chosen evaluation criteria and can be safely fixed or excluded from subsequent calibration stages.

Based on the results presented in Section, now we will use the argument `param.names` to create interaction figures only for the following parameters: `DDF`, `LPrat`, `FC`, `k0`, `lsuz`, `croute`, which were considered as the most sensitive parameters for this particular case study, based on expert judgement. Also, we will use the argument `dp3d.names` to create figures only for the `DDF`, `FC`, `k0` and `croute` parameters:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
  param.names= c("DDF", "LPrat", "FC", "k0", "lsuz", "croute"),
  dp3d.names= c("DDF", "FC", "k0", "croute"),
  do.png=TRUE, # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
  params.png.width=855, # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
  params.png.height=855, # 9.5 inches equals 855 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
  MinMax="max", # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
  beh.thr=0.3, # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
  ftype="dm", # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
  #nrows=5, # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
  FUN=mean, # function used to compute monthly values
  do.pairs=TRUE, # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
  gof.name="KGE2012", # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
  legend.pos="right", # position of the legend in the convergence plot
  main=main, # user-defined title for most of the output figures
  dotty.png.fname = "Params_DottyPlots-Reduced.png",
  hist.png.fname = "Params_Histograms-Reduced.png",
  bxp.png.fname = "Params_Boxplots-Reduced.png",
  ecdf.png.fname = "Params_ECDFs-Reduced.png",
  pruns.png.fname = "Params_ValuesPerRun-Reduced.png", #not used
  dp3d.png.fname = "Params_dp3d-Reduced.png"
)
```

```
## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3625 ]
```

```
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs          : 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 50 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 80 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
## [                                     ]
## [           Plotting ...           ]
## [                                     ]
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottyPlots-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun-Reduced.png' .. ]
## [ Plotting 3D dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]
## |
```

```
## [ Computing the UN-weighted ECDF for quantile 0.05 , 1/3=> 33.33% ... ]
## [ Computing the UN-weighted ECDF for quantile 0.5 , 2/3=> 66.67% ... ]
## [ Computing the UN-weighted ECDF for quantile 0.95 , 3/3=> 100% ... ]
## [
]
## [           Plots are finished !!
]
## [
]
```

9.5.3.1 Histograms

This figure shows **histograms** of sensitive model parameters, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 20: Histograms of parameter values for user-defined behavioural and sensitive parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.5.3.2 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of sensitive model parameters, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 21: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of sensitive parameter values for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.5.3.3 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of sensitive model parameters versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

Figure 22: Dotty plots showing the model performance of behavioural sensitive parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.5.3.4 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of sensitive parameter values, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (`KGE2012 >= beh_thr`). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)

Figure 23: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of sensitive parameter values. Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5, and vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5.

9.5.3.5 3D dotted plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo-three-dimensional dotted plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of sensitive model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 24: Three-dimensional dotted plots to explore the relationship between pairs of sensitive model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

9.6 Uncertainty analysis of calibration results

If you are not familiar with uncertainty analysis, you might be interested in Refsgaard et al. (2007), who review the terminology and typology of uncertainty, its interaction with the broader water management process and the role of uncertainty at different stages in the modelling processes.

9.6.1 Reading all calibration results

In order to proceed with the uncertainty analysis, we need to read all the calibrations results generated by hydroPSO during the optimisation. However, for this tutorial we are only interested in **behavioural parameter sets** (Beven, 2006; Beven & Binley, 1992; Beven & Freer, 2001), as defined by an arbitrary and user-defined goodness-of-fit value (i.e., a KGE2012 value). For this particular case, we choose `beh.thr=0.3`. Setting `beh.thr=0.3` and `MinMax='max'` will consider as behavioural all those parameter sets with goodness-of-fit values higher than the user-defined threshold 0.3:

```
res <- read_results(drtty.out=PSO.drtty.out, MinMax="max", beh.thr=0.3)

## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs : 3625 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 50 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 80 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
```

The next code chunk assigns all the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration (*params*), i.e., those with goodness-of-fit value higher than `beh.thr`; the goodness-of-fit value of each behavioural parameter set (*gofs*), the model outputs (i.e., streamflows for the TUWmodel case) corresponding to each behavioural parameter set (*Qsims*), the model output corresponding to the best parameter set obtained during calibration (*model.best*), and the observed values used in the calibration to compute the goodness-of-fit value (*model.obs*):

```
params    <- res[["params"]]
gofs      <- res[["gofs"]]
Qsims     <- res[["model.values"]]
model.best <- res[["model.best"]]
model.obs <- res[["model.obs"]]
```

9.6.2 Weighted quantiles of parameter values

The computation of weighted quantiles of model parameters would provide an estimate of the uncertainty in each model parameter, based on the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration and the goodness-of-fit values obtained for each one of them.

User-defined weighted quantiles for each model parameter are obtained multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model parameter based on all the behavioural parameter sets (i.e., for each column in `params`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the parameter set (*gofs*)³.

For this tutorial, we are going to use the `wquantile` function of `hydroPSO` to compute the 2.5, 50 and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each model parameter, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
params.025.50.975 <- wquantile(params, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                               normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
```

You might be interested in how far are the best parameter set found during the calibration from the median of the weighted behavioural parameter sets. In the following code chunk we will add a new column to `params.025.50.975`, just after the median (quantile 50):

```
params.025.50.best.975 <- cbind(params.025.50.975[, c(1,2)],
                                Best=as.numeric(best.param.cal),
                                params.025.50.975[, 3] )
colnames(params.025.50.best.975)[4] <- "97.5%"
round( params.025.50.best.975, 2)
```

	2.5%	50%	Best	97.5%
FALSE SCF	0.90	1.10	0.95	1.39
FALSE DDF	0.30	2.58	2.78	4.82
FALSE Twb	-2.84	0.36	2.33	2.60
FALSE Tm	-1.88	-0.22	-1.75	1.63
FALSE LPrat	0.15	0.77	0.90	1.00
FALSE FC	13.09	175.93	142.32	535.43
FALSE Beta	0.00	1.03	0.11	16.25
FALSE k0	0.05	0.37	0.40	1.92
FALSE k1	7.19	17.11	13.54	29.54
FALSE k2	30.00	143.17	34.17	249.60
FALSE lsuz	18.80	77.34	74.75	100.00
FALSE cperc	1.85	5.33	6.95	7.99
FALSE bmax	0.00	6.00	0.98	24.72
FALSE croute	3.21	23.87	24.88	43.46

³For more information about the computation of the weighted quantiles, please read `?wtd.stats`.

9.6.3 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

The computation of weighted quantiles of model simulations would provide an estimate of the uncertainty in each model simulated value (i.e., each daily streamflow), based on the goodness-of fit values obtained for the full time series simulated by the model.

User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model simulation based on all the model simulations (i.e., for each column in `Qsims`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the full time series simulated by the model (`gofs`).

For this tutorial, we are going use the `wquantile` function of `hydroPSO` to compute the 2.5, 50 and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each value simulated by the model, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
n <- ncol(Qsims)      # number of time steps

Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                              normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```
FALSE      2.5%   50% 97.5%
FALSE Sim1  2.050 3.612 5.436
FALSE Sim2  1.984 3.566 5.331
FALSE Sim3  1.930 3.520 5.252
FALSE Sim4  1.903 3.476 5.154
FALSE Sim5  1.844 3.434 5.079
FALSE Sim6  1.786 3.394 5.016
```

To plot the uncertainty bound for each model simulated value, we are going to transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```
dates.cal <- dip(Cal.Ini, Cal.Fin)
q025      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.cal)
q975      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.cal)
```

9.6.4 P-factor and R-factor

Now we are going to compute the **P-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percent of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bound:

```
( pf <- hydroGOF::pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.8220532
```

Also, we are going to compute the **R-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bound divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- hydroGOF::rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 1.049304
```

A good model should bracket most of the measured data (i.e., large P-factor, with a maximum of 1) with the smallest possible R-factor (minimum of 0).

9.6.5 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

Now we are ready to plot the *best* simulated streamflows along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds TUWmodel: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
Qobs.col <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col <- "lightblue"

Qsim.best.zoo <- zoo(model.best, time(Qobs.zoo.cal) )

plot(Qobs.zoo.cal, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [mm]")
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.cal) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.cal, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.best.zoo, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation
grid()
legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
      pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)
legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
      paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)
```


Figure 25: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the calibration period.

9.6.6 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

Now we are going to use the `fdcu` included in the `hydroTSM` R package to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the one of the *best* simulated streamflows, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period:

```
main.uncert <- paste0("FDC TUWmodel model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
bands.col   <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3,1), mar = c(2, 3.5, 1, 1), oma=c(0, 0, 0, 0), mgp=c(2, 0.75, 0) )
hydroTSM::fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo,
               bands.col=bands.col, main=main.uncert, log="")
grid()
hydroTSM::fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo,
               bands.col=bands.col, main="", log="y")
grid()
hydroTSM::fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo,
               bands.col=bands.col, main="", log="x")
grid()
```


Figure 26: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows (log='y') and the lower panel has focus on high flows (log='x').

9.6.7 Some comments about P-factor and R-factor

GLUE-like uncertainty analysis (Beven, 2006; Beven et al., 2008; Beven & Binley, 1992) is sensitive to the threshold used to define behavioural parameter sets (`beh.thr`). Lower thresholds usually retain more parameter sets and therefore produce wider posterior ranges for parameters and model simulations (Jin et al., 2010). This can increase the fraction of observations bracketed by the uncertainty band, but it may also reduce the sharpness and practical usefulness of the predictive interval.

In general, decreasing `beh.thr` tends to increase the P-factor, but this improvement is usually obtained at the expense of a larger R-factor. The two indicators should therefore be interpreted together: a high P-factor is desirable only when the associated uncertainty band remains sufficiently narrow for the intended hydrological application.

10 Verification analysis

10.1 Basic analysis of the verification period

Run `TUWmodel` with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration, but compute the goodness-of-fit only over the verification period:

```
P.zoo.ver <- window(P.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Ver, end=Ver.Fin)
Temp.zoo.ver <- window(Temp.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Ver, end=Ver.Fin)
PET.zoo.ver <- window(PET.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Ver, end=Ver.Fin)

P.ver <- as.numeric(P.zoo.ver)
Temp.ver <- as.numeric(Temp.zoo.ver)
PET.ver <- as.numeric(PET.zoo.ver)

Qobs.zoo.ver <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)
dates.ver <- time(Qobs.zoo.ver)
warmup.days.ver <- length(window(P.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Ver,
                                end=as.Date(Ver.Ini) - 1))

model.FUN.args.ver <- modifyList(
  model.FUN.args,
  list(
    obs = Qobs.zoo.ver,
    dates = dates.ver,
    warmup.days = warmup.days.ver,
    P = P.ver,
    Temp = Temp.ver,
    PET = PET.ver,
    Area = Area.m2
  )
)

modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = best.param.cal,
                           model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver)
```

Extract the simulated streamflow returned by `hydromodInR()`:

```
Qsim.zoo.ver <- modeloutput$sim
```

Graphical comparison of the **daily** observed and simulated time series obtained with the *best* parameter set for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 27: Graphical comparison of daily observed and simulated streamflow time series obtained with the extitbest parameter set obtained during the calibration.

This first visual comparison provides a preliminary indication of transferability, but the quantitative diagnostics and residual analyses below should be used to assess whether the calibrated parameter set performs satisfactorily outside the calibration period.

Graphical comparison of **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.ver}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.ver}$) values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 28: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 29: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **seasonal** simulated and observed values (one plot for each weather season) for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [mm]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 30: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Computing the **daily** residuals for the verification period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.ver - Qobs.zoo.ver
residuals <- window(residuals, start=Ver.Ini)
```

Plotting **daily, monthly and annual** time series, boxplots and histograms of the residuals for the verification period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 31: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Seasonal time series and boxplots of the residuals for the verification period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
          season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
          h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 32: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the seasonal scale.

10.2 Running behavioural parameter sets

Before running `TUWmodel` with the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration, we are going to use as model inputs only time series belonging to the independent verification period:

```
P.zoo.ver <- window(P.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Ver, end=Ver.Fin)
Temp.zoo.ver <- window(Temp.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Ver, end=Ver.Fin)
PET.zoo.ver <- window(PET.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Ver, end=Ver.Fin)
```

Storing the observed streamflows and dates used to evaluate the verification period:

```
Qobs.zoo.ver <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)
dates.ver <- time(Qobs.zoo.ver)
```

As mentioned before, `TUWmodel` does not support zoo objects as input data, and works with plain numeric values. Therefore, we need to transform the input time series into numeric objects:

```
P.ver <- as.numeric(P.zoo.ver)
Temp.ver <- as.numeric(Temp.zoo.ver)
PET.ver <- as.numeric(PET.zoo.ver)
warmup.days.ver <- length(window(P.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Ver,
                                end=as.Date(Ver.Ini) - 1))
```

The model arguments defined for the calibration period are updated so that the model is driven by the verification forcing and compared against the verification observations:

```
model.FUN.args.ver <- modifyList(
  model.FUN.args,
  list(
    obs = Qobs.zoo.ver,
    dates = dates.ver,
    warmup.days = warmup.days.ver,
    P = P.ver,
    Temp = Temp.ver,
    PET = PET.ver,
    Area = Area.m2
  )
)
```

Since `hydroPSO v0.5-0`, the `verification` function is fully compatible with R-based hydrological and environmental models. It can therefore be used to run `TUWmodel` with all behavioural parameter sets retained from the calibration stage. This step is useful for evaluating whether parameter sets that performed well during calibration also provide plausible simulations during an independent period.

The variable `verification.drty.out` represents the output directory that will store all the files generated by the `verification` function. It is not necessary to create this directory before running the calibration, because if this directory does not exist, it is automatically created by the `verification` function.

```
verification.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "verification")
```

Now, we run the verification process with all the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration:

```
out <- verification(fn = "hydromodInR",
  par = params,
  control = list(gof.name = "KGE2012", # Only used for identifying the name of the Go.
    MinMax = "max", # Indicates whether we are looking for minimum
    drty.out = verification.drty.out,
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "none",
    verbose = TRUE),
  model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `verification` have the same meaning as those of `hydroPSO` (more information can be found with `?verification`), with the exception of:

*) `par`: `data.frame` with all the parameter sets that will be run with `TUWmodel`. In this case, `params` was already read using a behavioural threshold equal to `beh.thr`.

10.3 Uncertainty analysis of verification results

10.3.1 Reading all verification results

In order to proceed with the uncertainty analysis, we need to read all the verification results generated by the previous call to the `verification` function:

```
gofs <- out[["gofs"]]
Qsims <- out[["model.values"]]
best.param.ver <- out[["best.param"]]
best.gof <- out[["best.gof"]]
```

10.3.2 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

The computation of weighted quantiles of model simulations would provide an estimate of the uncertainty in each model simulated value (i.e., each daily streamflow), based on the goodness-of-fit values obtained during the verification for the full time series simulated by the model.

User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model simulation based on all the model simulations (i.e., for each column in `Qsims`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the full time series simulated by the model during the verification period (`gofs`). For this tutorial, we are going to use the `wquantile` function of `hydroPSO` to compute the 2.5, 50 and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each value simulated by the model, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
n <- ncol(Qsims) # number of time steps

Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
  normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```
FALSE      2.5%   50% 97.5%
FALSE sim1 0.502 1.278 2.372
FALSE sim2 0.489 1.269 2.302
```

```
FALSE sim3 0.481 1.255 2.267
FALSE sim4 0.468 1.241 2.248
FALSE sim5 0.459 1.226 2.225
FALSE sim6 0.450 1.216 2.209
```

To plot the uncertainty bound for each value simulated during the verification period, we are going to transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```
dates.ver <- hydroTSM::dip(Ver.Ini, Ver.Fin)
q025      <- zoo::zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.ver)
q975      <- zoo::zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.ver)
```

10.3.3 P-factor and R-factor

Now we are going to compute the **P-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percent of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bound:

```
( pf <- hydroGOF::pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.7730798
```

Also, we are going to compute the **R-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bound divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- hydroGOF::rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.974513
```

A good model should bracket most of the measured data (i.e., large P-factor, with a maximum of 1) with the smallest possible R-factor (minimum of 0).

10.3.4 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

Now we are ready to plot the *best* simulated streamflows obtained during the verification along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds TUWmodel: ",
                     Qobs.stationname, " (" , Qobs.ID, ")")
Qobs.col    <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col   <- "lightblue"

plot(Qobs.zoo.ver, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [mm]") # empty plotting area
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.ver) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.ver, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.zoo.ver, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation during the verification
grid()

legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
       pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
       bty="n", cex = 1.2)
```

```

legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
                             paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

```


Figure 33: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the verification period.

10.3.5 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

Now we are going to use the `fdcu` included in the `hydroTSM` R package to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the one of the *best* simulated streamflows, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period:

```

( main.uncert <- paste0("FDC TUWmodel model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")") )

## [1] "FDC TUWmodel model: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)"
bands.col <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3, 1), mar = c(2, 3.5, 1, 1), oma=c(0, 0, 0, 0), mgp=c(2, 0.75, 0) )
hydroTSM::fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver,
               bands.col=bands.col, main=main.uncert, log="")

grid()
hydroTSM::fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver,
               bands.col=bands.col, main="", log="y")

grid()
hydroTSM::fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver,
               bands.col=bands.col, main="", log="x")

grid()

```


Figure 34: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows (log='y') and the lower panel has focus on high flows (log='x').

11 FAQ

11.1 How can I parallelise my computations?

You should use `parallel='parallel'` (for GNU/Linux or macOS operating systems) or `parallel='parallelWin'` (for MS Windows operating systems) in the `control` argument of the `hydroPSO` (Section 9.3) and/or `verification` (Section 10.2) functions.

In addition, there are two additional arguments that you should take care of (see details of the `control` argument in `?hydroPSO`):

- 1) **par.nnodes**: numeric, indicating the number of cores/CPU's to be used in the local multi-core machine, or the number of nodes to be used in the network cluster. By default `par.nnodes` is set to the amount of cores detected by the function `detectCores()` of the `parallel` package. If you are planning to use your computer while running the parallel computation, I suggest modifying its default value to `par.nnodes=detectCores()-2`. This argument can be omitted when `parallel='one'`, because it is not used at all.
- 2) **par.pkgs**: list of package names (as characters), not included in base R, that need to be loaded on each core/node for allowing the objective function `fn` to be evaluated. This argument can be omitted when `parallel='one'`, because it is not used at all.

The following two examples are provided to get an idea about the amount of reduction in computation time when using the parallel capability of `hydroPSO`. The two examples will be run first with the argument `parallel='none'` and then with `parallel='parallel'`, to compare the computation times. The two examples will be run with the same initial seed (`set.seed=1000`, to get exactly the same results), and without writing the results to disk (`write2disk=FALSE`), to speed up the comparison.

```
parallel <- "none"
write2disk <- FALSE
set.seed(1000)
( t1 <- system.time(
  out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR",
                 lower=lower, upper=upper, method="spsso2011",
                 control=list(write2disk=write2disk, MinMax="max", npart=80,
                              maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10,
                              parallel=parallel, reltol=1E-10),
                 model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
                 model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
  )
)

##   user  system elapsed
##  9.905   0.058   9.985
```

The next piece of code is used to detect the number of cores available in the machine that is being used for the computations, and set up a suitable number for `parallel` and `par.nnodes` arguments before running `hydroPSO`:

```
( detected.cores <- parallel::detectCores() )

## [1] 10
( parallel <- if ((is.na(detected.cores) || detected.cores <= 2)) {
  "none"
} else "parallel" )

## [1] "parallel"
( par.nnodes <- if (parallel == "none") 1 else detected.cores )

## [1] 10
par.pkgs <- c("TUWmodel", "zoo", "hydroPSO", "hydroTSM", "hydroGOF")

write2disk <- FALSE

set.seed(1000)
(t2 <- system.time(
  out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR",
                  lower=lower, upper=upper, method="sps2011",
                  control=list(write2disk=write2disk, MinMax="max", npart=80,
                               maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10,
                               parallel=parallel, par.nnodes=par.nnodes,
                               par.pkgs=par.pkgs, reltol=1E-10),
                  model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
                  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
                )
  )
)

##      user  system elapsed
## 15.150  20.376   9.140
```

The total reduction in the *elapsed times* (see `?proc.time`) when comparing the previous two running R processes was (as percentage):

```
reduction <- as.numeric(round(100 * (t1["elapsed"] - t2["elapsed"]) / t1["elapsed"], 1))

( paste0(reduction, "%") )

## [1] "8.5%"
```

The previous difference in execution time was not so large, because a single run of the `TUWmodel` is quite fast, and because `hydroPSO` was executed without writing the output files to the hard drive. However, even in this case this reduction in computation time can make an important difference for hydrological models with long running times.

Of course, for the same hydrological model and host machine, the total reduction in computation time will increase with increasing values of `par.nnodes`. However, if the value of `par.nnodes` is not so high (six or

less), **the use of parallel!=‘none’ might not be a good idea**, because of the overhead associated to the communication between the cores/nodes and the main algorithm.

You can also run `verification` in parallel using the same previous approach:

```
out <- verification(fn = "hydromodInR",
  par = params,
  control = list(gof.name = "KGE2012", # Only used for identifying the name of the Go.
    MinMax = "max", # Indicates whether we are looking for minimum
    drty.out = verification.drty.out,
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "parallel",
    par.nnodes = 5,
    par.pkgs = c("TUWmodel", "hydroPSO", "hydroGOF",
      "hydroTSM", "zoo", "data.table"),
    verbose = TRUE),
  model.FUN = TUWhydromod.basic,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

11.2 Why do I get some warnings after the calibration?

It is likely that you get some or more of the following warnings after finishing the calibration of `TUWmodel` with `hydroPSO`:

There are no pairs of ‘sim’ and ‘obs’ without missing values !

Warnings are often related to parameter sets that produce non-finite simulations, poor model performance, or numerical conditions that are outside the meaningful range of the hydrological model. In calibration experiments, some particles may visit regions of the parameter space that are hydrologically implausible even if they remain inside the numerical bounds defined by the user. The relevant point is to inspect whether the optimisation completed successfully and whether the final behavioural parameter sets produce meaningful streamflow simulations.

In the previously described cases, some parameter sets return `NA` when used to run `TUWmodel`. You might want to have a look to the `./PSO.out/Particles.txt` and `./PSO.out/Model_out.txt` files, to get the values of the parameter sets and the model outputs, respectively, that returned `NA` values.

If you want to reduce the number of warnings, you might explore to change some of the following `control` arguments: `Xini.type`, `boundary.wall...`

Parameter sets that produce `NA` during the optimisation are ignored during the calibration by `hydroPSO`, as you can verify comparing lines 20 (*Total model calls*) and 21 (*Effective model calls*) of the `./PSO.out/hydroPSO_logfile.txt` output file.

If you want to know the reason why a particular parameter set produces `NA`, please contact the maintainer of the `TUWmodel` package.

11.3 Why the KGE values shown by `ggof` does not match the one obtained during the optimisation?

The KGE value shown by `ggof` uses `method="2009"`. If the KGE you got during the optimisation is different from the one shown by `ggof`, very likely is due to the fact that you used `method="2012"` for the computation of KGE during the calibration.

11.4 Why do I get different results every time that I run `hydroPSO` with the same input data?

As mentioned in [Section 5](#), `hydroPSO` is a stochastic optimisation technique and, therefore, the initialisation of particles' position and the exploration of the parameter space is different every time that you run `hydroPSO`. That is the reason why you get different results (i.e., parameter sets and goodness-of-fit values) every time that you run `hydroPSO` with the same input data.

If you want to get the same results every time that you run `hydroPSO` (i.e., reproducibility) you should use `set.seed` with some numeric argument (e.g., `set.seed(100)`) just before calling `hydroPSO`.

11.5 How can I calibrate only a reduced number of model parameters?

Let's say that after looking at the figures obtained for the model parameters shown in [Section 9.5.2](#) you want to re-calibrate `TUWmodel` with all the parameters except `SCF` (position 1 in `param.values`), and we fix its value in `SCF=1.0`. For re-calibrating the remaining 13 parameters we should re-define the lower and upper bounds of your model parameters and the wrapper function you use for running your hydrological model ([Section 9.2](#)) as follows:

11.5.1 Model parameters to be calibrated

```
names <- c("DDF", "Twb", "Tm", "LPrat", "FC", "Beta",
           "k0", "k1", "k2", "lsuz", "cperc", "bmax", "croute")
lower <- c( 0.0, -3.0, -2.0, 0.0, 0, 0,
           0, 2, 30, 1, 0, 0, 0)
upper <- c( 5.0, 3.0, 2.0, 1.0, 600, 20,
           2, 30, 250, 100, 8, 30, 50)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

11.5.2 Wrapper R function

```
TUWhydromod.basic <- function(param.values, # Now it has 13 parameters instead of 15
                               obs=window(Qobs.zoo, start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
                               ) {
  # SCF=1.0, DDF, Tr=Twb, Ts=Twb, Tm, LPrat, FC, Beta, k0, k1, k2, lsuz, cperc, bmax, croute
```

```

param.values2 <- c(1.0, param.values[1:2], param.values[2:13])

# Evaluating the hydrological model at the 'param.values' parameter set
# P.cal, Temp.cal, PET.cal, and Area.m2 are used here as *global variables*
# (not good programming style, but it works)
simLump <- TUWmodel(param=param.values2, prec=P.cal, airt=Temp.cal, ep=PET.cal, area=Area.m2)

# Extracting only the numeric vector with simulations and observations
qsim.full <- as.numeric(simLump$q)
obs <- as.numeric(obs)

# Removing the warm-up period (one year, i.e., 365 days)
n <- length(qsim.full)
qsim <- qsim.full[366:n]
obs <- obs[366:n]

# Computing the goodness-of-fit value (i.e, model performance)
gof <- KGE(sim=qsim, obs=obs, method="2012")

# Creating the output of the R function
nelements <- 2
out <- vector("list", nelements)
out[[1]] <- gof
out[[2]] <- qsim.full

# Mandatory names for the elements of the output
names(out)[1:nelements] <- c("GoF", "sim")

return(out)
} # 'TUWhydromod.basic' end

```

11.5.3 Running the calibration

To calibrate TUWmodel with the previously defined 13 parameters and R wrapper functionb, we now run:

```

set.seed(1000)
out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR", lower=lower, upper=upper, method="sps02011",
               control=list(write2disk=TRUE, MinMax="max", npart=80, #Xini.type="sobol",
                             maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10, parallel="none",
                             reltol=1E-10),
               model.FUN="TUWhydromod.basic"
               )
( str(out) )

## List of 6
## $ par : Named num [1:13] 4.065 0.923 -0.277 0.789 2.895 ...
## .. attr(*, "names")= chr [1:13] "DDF" "Twb" "Tm" "LPrat" ...
## $ value : num 0.84
## $ best.particle: int 64
## $ counts : Named num [1:3] 4000 50 0
## .. attr(*, "names")= chr [1:3] "function.calls" "iterations" "regroupings"

```

```
## $ convergence : num 3
## $ message      : chr "Maximum number of iterations reached"
## NULL
```

11.5.4 Plotting results

```
plot_results(drty.out=PS0.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
  param.names= c("DDF", "LPrat", "FC", "k0", "lsuz", "croute"),
  dp3D.names= c("DDF", "FC", "k0", "croute"),
  do.png=TRUE, # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
  params.png.width=855, # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
  params.png.height=855, # 9.5 inches equals 855 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
  MinMax="max", # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
  beh.thr=0.3, # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
  ftype="dm", # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
  #nrows=5, # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
  FUN=mean, # function used to compute monthly values
  do.pairs=TRUE, # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
  gof.name="KGE2012", # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
  legend.pos="right", # position of the legend in the convergence plot
  main=main, # user-defined title for most of the output figures

  dotted.png.fname = "Params_DottyPlots-13params.png",
  hist.png.fname = "Params_Histograms-13params.png",
  bxp.png.fname = "Params_Boxplots-13params.png",
  ecdf.png.fname = "Params_ECDFs-13params.png",
  pruns.png.fname = "Params_ValuesPerRun-13params.png", #not used
  dp3d.png.fname = "Params_dp3d-13params.png"
)
```

```
## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3596 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 3596 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
```

```
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6940 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs          : 3596 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 50 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 80 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
## [
## [
## [          Plotting ...
## [
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottyPlots-13params.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms-13params.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots-13params.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs-13params.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun-13params.png' .
## [ Plotting 3D dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d-13params.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ...]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]
## |
```

11.5.4.1 Histograms This figure shows **histograms** of the 13 previously-defined model parameters previously defined, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLaferco (9414001)

Figure 35: Histograms of parameter values for the user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

11.5.4.2 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of the 13 previously-defined model parameters, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 36: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of the 13 model parameters for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

11.5.4.3 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of the 13 previously-defined model parameters versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

Figure 37: Dotty plots showing the performance of the behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) corresponding to the previously-defined 13 parameters. The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

11.5.4.4 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of the 13 previously-defined model parameters, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

TUWmodel: Rio Trancura antes de LLafenco (9414001)

Figure 38: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of the 13 previously-defined model parameters. Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5, and vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5.

11.5.4.5 3D dotted plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo-three-dimensional dotted plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of the 13 previously-defined model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 39: Three-dimensional dotted plots to explore the relationship between pairs of the 13 previously-defined model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

12 Software details

This tutorial was built under:

```
## [1] "aarch64-apple-darwin23"  
## [1] "R version 4.6.0 (2026-04-24)"  
## [1] "hydroPSO 0.5-58"  
## [1] "TUWmodel 1.1-1"  
## [1] "hydroGOF 0.7-0"  
## [1] "hydroTSM 0.8-6"  
## [1] "zoo 1.8-15"
```

13 Version history

-) v1.1: May 31th, 2026
-) v1.0: May 26th, 2026
-) v0.9.3: April 27th, 2020
-) v0.9.2: March 18th, 2020
-) v0.9.1: March 17th, 2020
-) v0.9: March 16th, 2020
-) v0.8: January 30th, 2020
-) v0.7: December 30th, 2019
-) v0.6: December 2017
-) v0.5: March 2017
-) v0.4: March 2016
-) v0.3: March 2015
-) v0.2: March 2014
-) v0.1: March 2013

References

- Abbaspour, K. C., Yang, J., Maximov, I., Siber, R., Bogner, K., Mieleitner, J., et al. (2007). Modelling hydrology and water quality in the pre-alpine/alpine Thur watershed using SWAT. *Journal of Hydrology*, 333(2-4), 413–430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2006.09.014>
- Abbaspour, K. C., Faramarzi, M., Ghasemi, S. S., & Yang, H. (2009). Assessing the impact of climate change on water resources in Iran. *Water Resources Research*, 45(10), W10434. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008WR007615>
- Abdelaziz, R., & Zambrano-Bigiarini, M. (2014). Particle Swarm Optimization for inverse modeling of solute transport in fractured gneiss aquifer. *Journal of Contaminant Hydrology*, 164, 285–298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconhyd.2014.06.003>
- Abdelaziz, R., Merkel, B. J., Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., & Nair, S. (2019). Particle swarm optimization for the estimation of surface complexation constants with the geochemical model PHREEQC-3.1.2. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-167-2019>
- Aguayo, R., Le'on-Muñoz, J., Aguayo, M., Baez-Villanueva, O. M., Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., Fern'andez, A., & Jacques-Coper, M. (2024). PatagoniaMet: A multi-source hydrometeorological dataset for Western Patagonia. *Scientific Data*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02828-2>
- Alvarez-Garreton, C., Mendoza, P. A., Boisier, J. P., Addor, N., Galleguillos, M., Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., et al. (2018). The CAMELS-CL dataset: Catchment attributes and meteorology for large sample studies-chile dataset. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 22(11), 5817–5846. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-22-5817-2018>
- Baez-Villanueva, O. M., Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., Mendoza, P. A., McNamara, I., Beck, H. E., Thurner, J., et al. (2021). On the selection of precipitation products for the regionalisation of hydrological model parameters. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 25(11), 5805–5837. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-25-5805-2021>
- Bergström, S. (1995). The HBV model. *Computer Models of Watershed Hydrology*.
- Beven, K. J. (2006). A manifesto for the equifinality thesis. *Journal of Hydrology*, 320(1-2), 18–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2005.07.007>
- Beven, K. J., & Binley, A. (1992). The future of distributed models - model calibration and uncertainty prediction. *Hydrological Processes*, 6(3), 279–298. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.3360060305>
- Beven, K. J., & Freer, J. (2001). Equifinality, data assimilation, and uncertainty estimation in mechanistic modelling of complex environmental systems using the GLUE methodology. *Journal of Hydrology*, 249(1-4), 11–29. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(01\)00421-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(01)00421-8)
- Beven, K. J., Smith, P. J., & Freer, J. E. (2008). So just why would a modeller choose to be incoherent ? *Journal of Hydrology*, 354(1-4), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2008.02.007>
- Ceola, S., Arheimer, B., Baratti, E., Blöschl, G., Capell, R., Castellarin, A., et al. (2015). Virtual laboratories: New opportunities for collaborative water science. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 19(4), 2101–2117.
- Cisty, M., & Soldanova, V. (2018). Flow prediction versus flow simulation using machine learning algorithms. In *International conference on machine learning and data mining in pattern recognition* (pp. 369–382). Springer.
- Gupta, H. V., Kling, H., Yilmaz, K. K., & Martinez, G. F. (2009). Decomposition of the mean squared error and NSE performance criteria: Implications for improving hydrological modelling. *Journal of Hydrology*, 377(1-2), 80–91.
- Hornberger, G. M., & Spear, R. C. (1981). Approach to the preliminary analysis of environmental systems. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 12(1), 7–18.
- Jin, X., Xu, C.-Y., Zhang, Q., & Singh, V. P. (2010). Parameter and modeling uncertainty simulated by GLUE and a formal Bayesian method for a conceptual hydrological model. *Journal of Hydrology*, 383(3-4), 147–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2009.12.028>
- Kennedy, J., & Eberhart, R. (1995). Particle swarm optimization. In *Proceedings of ICNN'95-international conference on neural networks* (Vol. 4, pp. 1942–1948). IEEE.
- Kling, H., Fuchs, M., & Paulin, M. (2012). Runoff conditions in the upper danube basin under an ensemble of climate change scenarios. *Journal of Hydrology*, 424, 264–277.
- Melsen, L. A., Addor, N., Mizukami, N., Newman, A. J., Torfs, P. J. J. F., Clark, M. P., et al. (2018). Mapping (dis)agreement in hydrologic projections. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 22(3), 1775–1791. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-22-1775-2018>

- Neri, M., Parajka, J., & Toth, E. (2020). Importance of the informative content in the study area when regionalising rainfall-runoff model parameters: The role of nested catchments and gauging station density. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, *24*(11), 5149–5171. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-24-5149-2020>
- Nijzink, Remko, Hutton, C., Pechlivanidis, I., Capell, R., Arheimer, B., Freer, J., et al. (2016). The evolution of root-zone moisture capacities after deforestation: A step towards hydrological predictions under change? *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, *20*(12), 4775–4799.
- Nijzink, RC, Almeida, S., Pechlivanidis, I., Capell, R., Gustafssons, D., Arheimer, B., et al. (2018). Constraining conceptual hydrological models with multiple information sources. *Water Resources Research*, *54*(10), 8332–8362.
- Parajka, J., Merz, R., & Blöschl, G. (2007). Uncertainty and multiple objective calibration in regional water balance modelling: Case study in 320 Austrian catchments. *Hydrological Processes*, *21*(4), 435–446. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.6253>
- Parajka, Juraj, Blaschke, A. P., Blöschl, G., Haslinger, K., Hepp, G., Laaha, G., et al. (2016). Uncertainty contributions to low-flow projections in austria. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, *20*(5), 2085–2101.
- Refsgaard, J. C., Sluijs, J. P. van der, Højberg, A. L., & Vanrolleghem, P. A. (2007). Uncertainty in the environmental modelling process - a framework and guidance. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, *22*(11), 1543–1556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2007.02.004>
- Rojas, R., & Zambrano-Bigiarini, M. (2012). *Tutorial for interfacing hydroPSO with SWAT-2005 and MODFLOW-2005*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3701891>
- Schuol, J., Abbaspour, K. C., Srinivasan, R., & Yang, H. (2008). Estimation of freshwater availability in the West African sub-continent using the SWAT hydrologic model. *Journal of Hydrology*, *352*(1-2), 30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2007.12.025>
- Sleziak, P., Szolgay, J., Hlavčová, K., & Parajka, J. (2016). The impact of the variability of precipitation and temperatures on the efficiency of a conceptual rainfall-runoff model. *Slovak Journal of Civil Engineering*, *24*(4), 1–7.
- Sleziak, Patrik, Szolgay, J., Hlavčová, K., Duethmann, D., Parajka, J., & Danko, M. (2018). Factors controlling alterations in the performance of a runoff model in changing climate conditions. *Journal of Hydrology and Hydromechanics*, *66*(4), 381–392.
- Sleziak, P., Szolgay, J., Hlavčová, K., Danko, M., & Parajka, J. (2020). The effect of the snow weighting on the temporal stability of hydrologic model efficiency and parameters. *Journal of Hydrology*, 124639.
- Széles, B., Parajka, J., Hogan, P., Silasari, R., Pavlin, L., Strauss, P., & Blöschl, G. (2020). The added value of different data types for calibrating and testing a hydrologic model in a small catchment. *Water Resources Res*, *56*(10), e2019WR026153. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019WR026153>
- Viglione, A., & Parajka, J. (2019). *TUWmodel: Lumped/semi-distributed hydrological model for education purposes*. Retrieved from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=TUWmodel>
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M. (2026a). *hydroGOF: Goodness-of-fit functions for comparison of simulated and observed hydrological time series*. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.hydroGOF>
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M. (2026b). *hydroTSM: Time series management and analysis for hydrological modelling*. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.hydroTSM>
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., & Baez-Villanueva, O. M. (2020). *Tutorial for using hydroPSO to calibrate TUW-model. Version 0.6*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3701903>
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., & Rojas, R. (2013). A model-independent Particle Swarm Optimisation software for model calibration. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, *43*, 5–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.01.004>
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., Clerc, M., & Rojas, R. (2013). Standard Particle Swarm Optimisation 2011 at CEC-2013: A baseline for future PSO improvements. In *2013 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation* (pp. 2337–2344). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEC.2013.6557848>
- Zessner, M., Schönhart, M., Parajka, J., Trautvetter, H., Mitter, H., Kirchner, M., et al. (2017). A novel integrated modelling framework to assess the impacts of climate and socio-economic drivers on land use and water quality. *Science of The Total Environment*, *579*, 1137–1151.